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European forum and oBsErvatory for OPEN science in transport

BE OPEN in a nutshell

Duration: 30 months

Start Date: 01-01-2019

Call: H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA

*Type of Action: Coordination and
Support Action*

GA Number: 824323

Overall Budget: € 1,997,283.75

EU Contribution: € 1,997,283.75

CONSORTIUM & THIRD PARTIES

(Third Parties)

MAIN FIGURES

- ✓ **17 partners**
- ✓ **8 third parties**
- ✓ **8 Work Packages**
- ✓ **32 Deliverables**

OBJECTIVES...

Capitalize upon existing initiatives enabling Open Science

- ✓ Key actors will coordinate and support actions for promoting OS policies, services and infrastructures
- ✓ Involve key actors in planning and implementation
- ✓ Enable key actors to learn from direct experience, previous knowledge and other stakeholders

OBJECTIVES...

Facilitate a common understanding among actors

- ✓ Promoting OS
- ✓ Prioritizing existing initiatives and actions at regional, European and International level

Monitor progress to improve Open Science exploitation

- ✓ Indicators will be developed for supporting OS purposes
- ✓ Monitoring process to address information management, internal and external coordination, risk management and other dimensions

TRANSPORT FORUM/OBSERVATORY FOR PROMOTING OPEN SCIENCE

MEGA THEMES

RESULTS

Reviewed scientific sources and produced a **systematic taxonomy of key actors**, a unified transport terminology and related research and instruments

Produced a **framework of common understanding of OS in the transport research**

Described and classified **use cases affecting current and future research trends and related industrial developments** in the transport arena

RESULTS

4

Conducted a **mapping of open access publications**, policy and repository in European transport research

5

Reviewed the **use of Open data and software in European transport research** as well as the **existence of business models** for infrastructure of Open Science

6

Summarized the challenges and opportunities for **aligning Transport research with EOSC**

RESULTS

Prepared the knowledge in transport research for the future by **proposing governance model for Open Science in European transport research**

Developed the **membership and governance scheme of the TOPOS forum and observatory**

Achieved a cooperation with the **OSCAR project** & Initiated a collaboration with the **Blue-Cloud** and the **FNS projects**

PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Support in fully modern OS services in transport research
through the TOPOS Forum and Observatory tools
for the research community, industry and society/citizens.

Dealing with behavioral issues and user needs
by i) focusing on the objectives and priorities of stakeholders, ii)
developing governance and new operational/business models and iii)
describing how to create and capture value in economic and social
context

PROGRESS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Development of appropriate **regulatory frameworks and policies to support innovation and deployment**
i.e. the European Code of Conduct on OS in transport research

Engagement of international stakeholders for mutual learning and sharing experiences for operationalizing OS principles in transport research

ADVISORY BOARD

Top independent experts will ensure that the project is progressing along the correct path

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